

Hybrid workshop: 'Policy coherence for Sustainable Development'

MATS Deliverable 4.4

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Funded by
the European Union

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Summary

Deliverable 4.4. was originally foreseen as an online webinar but was expanded to a full day hybrid workshop taking place both online and in person at the University of Maastricht on the 1st of March, 2024. It brought together MATS and external experts together to discuss the legal dimensions of agricultural trade between the EU and other partners, with an emphasis on policy coherence for development.

The first session discussed general issues of trade concerning the EU (unilateral measures in agricultural trade, FTAs, etc.). The second session focused on the intersections between agriculture and environment in trade agreements. The third session took the form of a roundtable on aspects related to intellectual property rights and agricultural trade.

The outcomes of the hybrid workshop were presented in person during the MATS project meeting in Brussels on the 7th of March 2024.

Deliverable title: Webinar 'Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development'

Deliverable number: D.4.4

Authors: Sylvia Kay

Due date: 31 March 2024

Submission date: 29 March 2024

Nature¹ : O

Dissemination Level² : PU

Work Package: 6

Lead Beneficiary: TNI

Contributing Beneficiaries: University of Maastricht (UM), SEATINI

¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Programme

Introduction and Keynote: General Issues in EU and Trade

11.00-11.15: Introduction (University of Maastricht)

11.15-11.45: Keynote by John Clarke

11.45-12.15: Open Debate

BREAK

Session 2: Agricultural Trade and Environment

Moderator: Sylvia Kay (TNI)

14.00-14.20: Dr Saker El Nour

14.20-14.40: Dr Raffaele D'Annolfo

14.40-15.00: Dr Gustavo Ribeiro

15.00-15.30: Open Debate

BREAK

Roundtable on Intellectual Property Rights in Trade and Agriculture

16.00-16.30: Rob Huijten

16.30-17.00: Araken Alves Lima

17.00-17.30: Open Debate

17.30-17.40: Concluding remarks (University of Maastricht)

Key discussion points

The hybrid workshop highlighted in particular four areas of policy *incoherence* for development concerning the EU and agricultural trade that are relevant for the MATS consortium and work. These include:

First, as raised by former trade negotiator for the EC, John Clarke, in his keynote address, we are witnessing an increasing failure of multilateral trade negotiations and, as a result, a shift unilateral measures in trade policy. A discussion ensued as to what this trend entails for policy coherence for development? A number of challenges were raised with regards to the difficulties, without a robust, updated multilateral trade framework, to ensure a set of universal minimum standards are respected. However, there are also positive signs, such as the inclusion of a new dedicated chapter on Sustainable Food Systems and Animal Welfare in the recent EU-New Zealand free trade agreement.

Second, in the domain of agricultural trade and the environment, two sticking points were raised. The first is that there are patterns of unequal ecological exchange (the intensive and extractive use of natural resources) between the EU and other regions of the world, such as North Africa, which was the focus on the interventions of two speakers in this session. Both Saker El Nour (who has contributed to TNI's MATS Case Study No.15) and Raffaele D'Annolofò (from another EU Horizon project 'Trade4SD') raised the issue of the trade in olive oil between Tunisia and the EU which relies on water intensive monocultural olive tree cultivation in Tunisia, a country which is facing water scarcity and increasing drought.

The other issue is that when it comes to trade in environmental goods, there is still no consensus on what constitutes an environmental good in trade policy as witnessed by the failure of the Environmental Goods Agreement. As outlined by the speaker, Gustavo Ribeiro from the University of Brasilia, Brazil, this has significant implications for how environmental aspects of trade agreements are approached and how

trade agreements interface with key climate and biodiversity related global agreements.

Third, and finally, the issue of intellectual property rights and trade was discussed. Here, there was a focus on the seed and biofuels industries. Here, the main issue of debate was around the rights enshrined for particular actors and if these conflict and are in tension with the rights of other vulnerable and marginalised groups, for example around the issue of plant breeders' rights and farmer saved seed exchanges.

Further links, Participants list, The meeting flyer

Link to webinar announcement and programme: <https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/workshop-legal-dimensions-of-agricultural-trade-and-sustainability-on-1st-of-march-2024/>

The list of participants registered:

No.	Name	Organization
1	Facundo,Calvo	Geneva,CH,International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD),Agriculture Trade Policy Analyst,Switzerland
2	Oluzhen,Chen	University of Helsinki,researcher ,Finland
3	Andrea,Zuniga,	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna di Pisa,PhD candidate in Agro-environmental law
4	Mari,Carlson,	Geneva,CH,University of Helsinki,Coordinator, Switzerland
5	Christian,Haberli,	Geneva,CH,WTI,Trade and Agricultural Climate Law Expert,Switzerland
6	Ariane,Vogelhuber-Slavinsky	Karlsruhe,DE,Fraunhofer ISI,Researcher,Germany
7	Araken,Lima,	BR,Brazilian National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI-BR),Head of Regional Division for IP Dissemination - State of Santa Catarina,Brazil
8	Douglas,Alves Santos,	BR,Casa,Patent Examiner,Brazil,INPI
9	Nilda ,Moreno,Ilheus	BR,Casa N ,CEO - Founder ,Brazil
10	Ana,Paula Gomes Pinto	Rio de Janeiro,BR,Maastricht University,PhD Candidate,Brazil,Maastricht University
11	Keliane,Miranda de Freitas	,Ministério da Agricultura,Eng. Agrônoma,Brazil,Ministério da Agricultura e Pecuária do Brasil
12	Jane ,Nalunga,	Kampala,UG,SEATINI,Executive Director ,Uganda
13	Hoseana Bohela,Lunogelo,I	Dar-es-salaam,TZ,ESRF-Economic and Social Research Foundation,Principal Research Associate,Tanzania
14	Alemu,Hawitibo	,Addis Ababa,ET,Addis Ababa University ,Ass. Prof.,Ethiopia
15	Brian,Sserunjogi,	KAMPALA,UG,"Economic Policy Research Centre, Makerere University",Research Fellow,Uganda
16	Sanday,Amos,	ESRF,Research Associate
17	Justine,Luwedde,	Kampala,UG,Economic Policy Research Centre,Research Analyst,Uganda
18	Fulgence,Mishili,	Morogoro,TZ,Sokoine University of Agriculture,"Senior Ag. Economist and HoD, Agricultural Economics and Agribusiness ",Tanzania
19	PETER,PHILIP,	Morogoro,TZ,Sokoine University of Agriculture,Tutorial Assistant,Tanzania
20	Marie,Rau,	Berlin,DE,,Germany,Research
21	Mario,Saade,	Brasília,BR,ApexBrasil,Analyst,Brazil
22	Belén,Gracia,	Maastricht ,NL,Maastricht University ,PhD,Netherlands,PhD Candidate
23	Gustavo,Ribeiro,	Brasília,BR,CEUB (University Center of Brasília),Professor,Brazil

24	Giovanni Dall'Agnola ,	Geneva,CH,Geneva Graduate Institute,PhD Researcher in International Law ,Switzerland,'-
25	Kenny ,Cetera,	Jakarta,ID,World Resources Institute,Consultant,Indonesia
26	Ananda Putri ,Permatasari,	Jakarta,ID,WRI Indonesia,'-',Indonesia,'-
27	Emanuel Mbazzi,Msemo,	Morogoro,TZ,Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA),PhD student,Tanzania
28	K,Tyagi	Maastricht,NL,Maastricht University,Assistant Professor,Netherlands
29	Sophia,Van maren,	Maastricht,NL,UM,Lecturer,Netherlands,Interested in trade and agriculture.
30	Roselyne,Alphonce,	Morogoro,TZ,Sokoine University of Agriculture,lecturer,Tanzania
31	Sofia,Tenorio Fenton,	Washington DC,US,World Resources Institute,"Engagement Specialist, Supply Chains",United States
32	Joshua,Mkuji MOROGORO,	TZ,SUA,ASSISTANT LECTURER,Tanzania
33	Cecilia ,Hasher Vila Velha	BR,Prospective ,CEO,Brazil,INPI
34	NEEMA,KUMBURU,	Moshi-Helsinki,TZ,Moshi Co-operative University,Associate Professor,Tanzania
35	Mauro ,Luz,São Paulo ,	BR,Mdic,Analist,Brazil
36	Leonardo,Cunha Silva ,	Maastricht ,NL,University of Sao Paulo ,PhD Candidate,Netherlands
37	Ilknur ,Unuvar	,Ankara,TR,Ankara University,Assisst. Prof.,Turkey
38	Francesco ,Cazzini,	Brussels ,BE,Wageningen University ,Lecturer,Belgium
39	Saker,El Nour,Lille Franc	FR,Reseau TANMO,Program director ,France,tni case studies research coordination
40	Anselm,Kamperman Sanders,	Maastricht,NL,UM,Prof. of law,Netherlands
41	Bodo,Steiner,	Helsinki,FI,University of Helsinki,Professor
42	Roberto,Henke,	Roma,IT,CREA,Senio Researcher,Italy
43	Sylvia,Kay,Den Haag,	NL,TNI,Project Officer,Netherlands
44	Federica ,Morandi ,	Roma ,IT,CREA,Research grant ,Italy,TRADE4SD
45	Maria Rosaria,Pupo D'Andrea,	Rende,IT,CREA,Senior researcher,Italy
46	Raffaele,D'Annolfo,	Roma,IT,CREA,Ricercatore,Italy,Trade4SD
47	Sara ,Romano,	Roma,IT,Università degli Studi della Tuscia,Dottoranda,Italy,CREA team
48	federica,demaria,	Rome,IT,CREA-PB,Researcher,Italy
49	Zimmer,Gomes,	Brasília,BR,ApexBrasil,Analyst,Brazil
50	Dalindyebo,Shabalala ,	Boston,US,Suffolk University law school,Professor,United States
51	Igor,Silva,	Brasília,BR,ApexBrasil,Analista,Brazil
52	Yusuph ,Kulindwa,	Dar es Salaam ,TZ,Moshi cooperative University ,Lecturer ,Tanzania

The webinar flyer:

Deliverable WP 4.4: Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development

Workshop 'Legal Dimensions of Agricultural Trade and Sustainability'

ONLINE via Zoom

1 March 2024
CET TIME 11:00-17:40h

The online workshop takes place on the 1st of March, bringing MATS and external experts together to discuss the legal dimensions of agricultural trade between the EU and other partners.

The first session will discuss general issues of trade concerning the EU (unilateral measures in agricultural trade, FTAs, etc.).

The second session will focus on general issues of agriculture and environment in trade agreements.

The third session will be a roundtable on intellectual property aspects of agricultural trade.

WEBSITE

[Register here](#)

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